

The Church of Nigeria Anglican Communion

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The Anglican Church in Nigeria is a Christian English Church with the root in Church of England. She has members spread across every geopolitical zone in Nigeria. Although the church population is said to be about 18.74million members according to Journal of Anglican Studies published by Cambridge University Press her active membership is put at just over 11 million adherents. The Anglican Church in Nigeria has a rich history that dates back to the 19th century. The Anglican Church's presence in Nigeria can be traced back to the arrival of British missionaries in the mid-19th century. The Church Missionary Society (CMS) played a significant role in the establishment and growth of the Anglican Church in Nigeria during this time. The history of the Church began from 1842 when the Church Missionary Society (CMS) ably led by Henry Townsend landed in Badagry, Western part of Nigeria. Missionaries such as Samuel Ajayi Crowther, who later became the first African Anglican bishop in Nigeria, were instrumental in spreading the Anglican faith across the country. The Anglican Church in Nigeria grew steadily throughout the colonial period, and its influence expanded as it established schools, hospitals, and other social institutions. The church also played a significant role in the spread of Western education in Nigeria. Following Nigeria's independence in 1960, the Anglican Church continued to grow and evolve, becoming an integral part of the country's religious and social fabric. The church has been involved in various social and political issues and has contributed to the development of Nigeria in numerous ways. Today, the Anglican Church in Nigeria is one of the largest Christian denominations in the country, with millions of members. It has its own hierarchy of Primate, Archbishops, Bishops, clergy, and dioceses, and it remains an influential force in Nigerian society. The Anglican Church in Nigeria continues to be active in various areas, including education, healthcare, and social welfare, and it plays a vital role in the spiritual and moral life of the Nigerian people. Its involvement in higher education propelled the establishment of Universities in Nigeria. Prominent among these Universities are Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo in western part of Nigeria and St Paul's University, Awka in the Eastern part of the country. Currently the Anglican Church in Nigeria comprises of one hundred and sixty-one dioceses (161) with Bishops overseeing them. These dioceses are arranged into 14 Ecclesiastical Provinces under the administration of Archbishops and being supervised by the Primate of Church of Nigeria, Anglican Communion; The Most Revd Henry Chukwudum Ndokuba. The past Archbishops and Primate of Church of Nigeria include The Most Revd T.O. Olufosoye, The Most Revd J.A. Adetiloye, The Most Revd P.J. Akinola and The Most Revd Nicholas Okoh. Apart from its effort in promoting health, welfare and Western education in Nigeria, the Church of Nigeria (Anglican Communion), operates standard training Institutions for the theological education and spiritual and pastoral formation of its priests. Currently, the church has eight (8) Theological colleges spread across the country. The theological sector is headed by the Bishop Theologian, The Rt Revd Dapo Asaju and Each Theological College is headed by a Rector, but supervised by Governing Boards chaired by appointees of their respective proprietors.

Date Range: 1842 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Nigeria

Region tags: Nigeria, Africa

Nigeria, West Africa. Most Nigerian Pentecostals live in southern Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Fape, M. Olusina 2009. *Knowing The Fundamentals of Anglicans; A Basic Approach to Anglican Studies* (Sagamu; JOAS Press)
- Source 2: Kwashi, Benjamin A 2013, "The Church of Nigeria Anglican Communion" In Ian S. Markham et Al (Ed's.), *The Wiley-Blackwell Companion to the Anglican Communion* (Malden; Wiley-Blackwell)
- Source 3: Oyebanjo, Peter Adelaja 2021. *Theology of the Cross; Its Teaching and Practices in the Anglican Liturgy and Spirituality* (Osogbo; Kings and Queens Publisher)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.rpl.hds.harvard.edu>fag>.
- Source 1 Description: "Anglicanism in Nigeria," 2013, In *Religious and Public Life*.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.sjbts.org>.
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- Source 1 URL: <https://www.anglicanpastor.com>
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- Source 3 URL: <https://www.sjbts.org>
- Source 3 Description: Dinovo, D.R. 2009. *An Explanation and Guide to Anglicanism*

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Other religious groups are in cultural contact with the church. This is evident as the Church of Nigeria Anglican Communion operates within a Nigeria which is a secular state.

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact in Nigeria is competitive because different religious groups proselytise within the boundaries of the country. These groups all target the same population

of residents in the country during their proselytising campaigns. This makes the cultural contact competitive.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Though all the religious groups which consider proselytising a cardinal aspect of their operations target the same population for conversion into their fold, they mostly go about their proselytising campaigns with maturity without causing violence. However, parts of northern Nigeria, are noted for religious intolerance and violent conflicts. The conflicts are usually between violent Islamic groups and other vulnerable religious (Christian) denominations.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Children who are born by parents who identify as members of the church have some form of membership status imputed on them until they become adults. They are then free to decide to continue as members or discontinue if they so please.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: There are no class considerations in deciding on who becomes members of the church.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

Notes: Women are not allowed to be ordained as priest

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Some of these rituals are Religious and rite of passage

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Before Nigeria got independence from their colonial administration under Britain, the church of England as it was then known had some form of political support from the government of the time. However, though they have several of their members occupying political offices, it cannot be said that the church has an official political support above other religious groups in the country.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 11000000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 4.89

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (with smaller religious groups not officially allowed but in practice tolerated)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The church has an organised clerical structure with the Primate at the apex. He is followed by the archbishops, then the bishops. Beneath these top level clergy are other classes of clergy including Venerable, Rev'd Canon, Rev'd, evangelists etc.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

Notes: Although there is a clergy who leads each congregation but depending on the size of the local assembly, there may be two or three clergy posted to work there under the leadership of the most senior in the group.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the

sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The Primate is the overall leader of the Church of Nigeria Anglican Communion in the country.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The council of bishops oversees the ecclesiastical church in the sample region.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 8

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Although members who want to enter into the class of the clergy may so indicate and undergo training as priests, their promotion after placement in churches is determined by their respective bishops.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

Notes: The bishop promotes, rather prefers clergy under their diocese to the next clerical rank. However, to become a bishop, the council of bishops must approve such

preferment.

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: Though leaders are considered fallible, members do hardly take a hard stand against them proclaiming their errors in such manner that destroys their standing in the church body as a whole.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This could happen but it seldom does.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: Politicians do not have a role to play in the administration of the church.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

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↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

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↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

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– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 30

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 250

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 30

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 20

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 15

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 50

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Field doesn't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Only religious public space
- Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Items such as Dove and fish are used symbolically

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Such heroes of faith

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that the spirit and the body are two components that make up the human being.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: While the spirit cannot be caught, handled or grabbed the body can be seen, felt and handled.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: The church does not believe in re-incarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: A Supreme God that has divine relationship with his people

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The group sees monarchs as manifestations of the supreme being just as other humans are.

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: He is kind, benevolent and omnipotent

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: he has knowledge of everything and everyone in the world as the creator of the universe.

- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample

region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Because He is believed to have created the world.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: He does this only to achieve a good purpose to punish wrongdoing and prune, trim humans when they are beginning to or already in the habit of disobeying God's good commands.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: He is also the judge of the world. He has absolute powers over the created order.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: He can communicate with anybody that is in alignment with him

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: revelations ,trance ,hecycop ,Sermons ,dreams
Through

Notes: We

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme God is believed to have relationship with humans as humans are created in his image even though he cannot be seen.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: He is just as all other humans are.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: He is benevolent and supplies all needs of his adherents when they faithfully serve him

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

–Yes [specify]: He is omnipotent, omniscient and omnipresent

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: His knowledge is not restricted. That is why believers refer to him as Omniscient

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: He is believed to know everything in the whole universe

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: His knowledge is not restricted

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: UniverseUnov the of creator the being dworl ownunknother of itiesactiv the owskn He

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Especially to sins and errors

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: In his 10 commandments he commanded not to have or serve another god

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: ly rdingacco powers other texhibi He

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Like pastors and prophets
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: cyrophe and devotion personal, yersPra oughThr
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The non-human supernatural beings include angels, heavenly creatures, the twenty four elders and demons under the control of Satan, the arch enemy of God
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Except when they intentionally want to.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what

you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: They have knowledge of events which happened in the distant past which human beings are not aware of.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They are not restricted by the forces of nature as human beings are.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: This applies to some non-human supernatural beings which are loyal to Satan. For example, some are principalities, powers, rulers of the darkness of this world and spiritual wickedness in high places.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

Notes: The supernatural beings which the group believes in do not care about food taboos. However, some supernatural beings of other groups in their locality do care about taboos.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: They do not take kindly to desecration of holy/sacred spaces.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: They care about the handling of sacred objects like the bible etc.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Yes [specify]: Bestiality and homosexuality.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– Yes [specify]: Loving other people

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural punishments are coordinated by the supreme being though he may delegate the act in some cases.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - No

Notes: They may be delegated by the supreme being to carry out the task of rewarding deserving individuals as the supreme being pleases.

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - No
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:
– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Coming on specified date:
– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:
– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:
– No

↳ Coming has already passed:
– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: To save adherents from death, calamity and end-time suffering.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: ctioninjun edivin to ceadherenrentsadhe tStric

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– Yes

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
 - Yes
- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
 - Yes
- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
 - No
- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
 - No
- ↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
 - Yes

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
 - All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - Yes
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes

- ↳ Generosity / charity:
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
– Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):
– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:
– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:
– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Same sex marriages are not allowed in the group. In fact, it was a major point of disagreement between the church of Nigeria Anglican Communion which disagreed with the idea of same sex marriages and the Church of England which supported the idea. In the heat of the crisis, the church of Nigeria Anglican Communion led other churches affiliated to the Church of England in Africa to break ties with the latter.

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Same sex marriages are not allowed in the group. In fact, it was a major point of disagreement between the church of Nigeria Anglican Communion which disagreed with the idea of same sex marriages and the Church of England which supported the idea. In the heat of the crisis, the church of Nigeria Anglican Communion led other churches affiliated to the Church of England in Africa to break ties with the latter. Bestiality is also disapproved by the church

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: The group believes that all food substances are provided by God. Humans are therefore free to eat of all food items.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: The group does not subscribe to unnecessary physical risk taking. All risks to be taken are meant to achieve a positive end.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Members of this group are encouraged to have personal and family prayer meetings and times to study the bible.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 12

Notes: They are encouraged to pray at least twice daily. This is usually to be carried out first thing in the morning and just before bed at night.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: The church holds regular weekly, monthly, quarterly and annual conventions/meetings.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100

Notes: The total number of participants in each meeting depends on the target audience, the parish location etc

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Notes: The interval of 168 hours between meetings only represents weekly programmes of the church. For programmes holding monthly, quarterly or yearly, the interval between such programmes will be longer.

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Orthodoxy checks are sometimes observed during congregational prayers and other programmes.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A Country

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: The group does not provide public food storage. It may sometimes partner with good spirited individuals to facilitate the provision of public food storage to communities which are in need of them.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: It is provided by the government

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: The church encourages members to pay their tithes and to give offerings and special collections. Such moneys are used to pay clergy stipends and to develop the church.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government levies taxes on the citizens including members of the church.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: When the offense committed is a capital offense. This must be proven in a court of competent jurisdiction.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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